

ETYMOLOGY OF THE WORD «SAMARKAND» IN THE ETHNOCULTURE OF THE SAMARKAND OASIS

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ABSTRACT

This article provides information about the ancient history and civilization of the Samarkand oasis. The scientific views of ancient sources and historians on the origin and etymology of the word Samarkand are also comparatively analyzed. In addition, the ancient inhabitants of the Samarkand oasis and their significance in the formation of the ethnic culture of the oasis are revealed.

INTRODUCTION. The territory of Uzbekistan is considered one of the places where the first civilizations were formed not only in Central Asia, but also in the Ancient Eastern world. Among them are the ancient Khorezm, Bactrian, Sogdian, Shosh and Ferghana civilizations, many objects of material, cultural and archaeological heritage associated with them have been studied. Presenting the results of these studies to the world community is a topical issue today.

Studies show that these civilizations are based on urban processes, that is, the formation and development of the first urban culture and the first state associations. The formation and development of ancient civilizations is not a spontaneous historical process, they were formed in specific historical conditions and have their own historical roots. From this point of view, we present the primary sources and data obtained in the studies of subsequent years regarding the historical roots of the ancient civilization of the Zeravshan oasis.

LITERATURE REVIEW. It should be noted that in the scientific analysis of the Samarkand oasis, first of all, it is necessary to pay attention to the etymology of the word Samarkand, its origin. The Samarkand oasis is located in the middle part of the Zeravshan river basin. The Zeravshan valley is surrounded from the north by the spurs of the Turkestan Range. The valley descends from east to west and connects with the Kyzylkum desert in the northeast and Karnabchel in the southwest.

The earliest information about Samarkand is given in «Avesta», where the Zeravshan oasis is described by two terms - «Suguda» and «Suguda Gova». According to experts, the concept of «Suguda Gova» refers to the settlements of the Zeravshan oasis, while the term «Sugdi» is used in relation to cities and the capital. At the time of the Avesta, Samarkand was undoubtedly the largest city and capital of Sogd. [1; P.434]

Firdowski Afrosiab is described in Shakhnom as the king of the country of Turan. Afrosiab bears the name Frangrasyan in the Avesta, and Alp Er Tonga in Turkish sources. If there were no connection between the ruins of Afrosiab and the leader of the «types» Afrosiab, his name would not be called «Afrosiab». «Avesta» testifies that the battle between the «Turians» and the Medes led by Afrosiab took place near Lake Chaychista (Arole) in the 8th century BC. It is a historical fact that the period of the formation of the city fell at the same time when Afrosiab entered the historical scene. [2; P.191]

In the book of Abu Rayhan Beruni «Kanuni Masudi» it is explained that «Samarkand is Samizkent in Turkish, one of the cities of enlightenment». Mahmud Koshgari in his work «Devonu Lugatit Turk» (11th century): «The Oguzes and those who are close to them. Because of its size, Samarkand is called samizkent - a fat city. Persians use it in the manner of Samarkand» [3; P.330], - writes academician V. Bartold also wrote that «Mahmud Koshgari semizkent - «a rich city» recorded the Turkic etymology in his work «Turks». [4; P.65] «Some European scientists deduce the name of the city from the Sanskrit word Samaria - «meeting», «congress»

[5; P.5], writes S.Koraev.

Also in the writings of ancient Greek historians, Samarkand was first mentioned by Arrian under the name «Marokanda». Arrian wrote: «Alexander moved north very slowly with his army and all his chariots. After fulfilling the obligation received by the local population to supply horses to his troops, he left for Marokanda». [6; P.192]

According to Professor T.Shirinov, «... the name Samarkand in Arabic or Persian was analyzed, but no attention was paid to its pronunciation in the ancient Sogdian language «Samarakan». If T.Shirinov: «In any case, the interpretation of the term «Samarkand» in connection with the name of a person is far from historical truth. It is also wrong to look for an explanation from the Arabic language, because a thousand years before the arrival of the Arabs, the city was known as Samarkand», Professor T.Nafasov wrote seven interpretations in his article «Samarkand polysonyms» related to the meaning of the name Samarkand linguistic analysis. [7; P.57-58] Researcher T.Ernazarov also noted that the word «samar» has such meanings as «name of a person», «name of a commander», «well», «fruit-harvest». [8; - B.51 - 52]

Khoja Abu Zakariyo Varagsari in his work «Kandiya» claims that the origin of the etymology of Samarkand was caused by the order of the legendary person. That is, Samarkand was ruled by the legendary ruler Shamar ibn Khoris, and he founded a city called «Shamarkat». Then this name is changed to Samarkand. [9; P. 39]

DISCUSSION. According to Greek historians, including Quintus Curtius Rufus, when Alexander the Great conquered Samarkand in 329 BC, the defense was strong, the city prospered, and the people were brave, highly cultured and noble. The local Sogdians, led by Spitamen, put up strong resistance to Alexander's troops, who invaded Central Asia.

In our opinion, Greek historians recognized the inhabitants of the city of Marokanda as Sogdians, which means that the Sogdians are the ancient inhabitants of today's Samarkand.

It is known from research that at the beginning of the 1st millennium BC Sogd and its capital Samarkand existed as an administrative region. «In ancient Sanskrit, the term «smrg» meant «crossroads», «trade crossroads», «a place where merchants meet». In our opinion, the

interpretation of the term «Samarkand» as a crossroads of trade routes, a crossroads, a prosperous city is quite close to the truth. No wonder the name of one of the old quarters of the city is called «Crossroads» [10; P.191] writes Professor T.Shirinov. A.Sadullaev and M.Isakov share a similar opinion.

IX-X centuries occupy an important place in the history of Movarounnahr, including the oasis and the city of Samarkand. During this period, Sogd (Sugdiana) was considered one of the most economically and culturally developed countries of Movarounnahr. Before the Arab conquest, Sogd was a state that included the Zeravshan valleys (except the Bukhara oasis) and the Kashkadarya valleys, and the king of Sogd was in Samarkand, the capital. During the reign of the encyclopedist Abu Rayhan Beruni (973-1048), only the Zeravshan valley was called Sugd. According to Alloma, in the Sughd region, which is among the places of the fifth climate, the cities of Karmana (Karminia), Dobusia, Kushaniya, Isbanjon, Arbinjon, Nasaf (Nakhlakh), Kash (Kesh), Samarkand were mentioned. [11; P.424]

The author of the work «Khudud ul-Olam», written in Persian (982-983), the geographer Abu-l-Kharis Muhammad ibn Ahmad, argued that Sogd, where the Sogds lived, was a region located in the basins of Zerafshan and Kashkadarya. in antiquity and the Middle Ages and corresponds to the northern regions of Tajikistan. [12; P.27] The author also admits that there is no more sacred place in the eastern regions of the Sughd region. He describes Sogd as a place with a lot of flowing water and trees, healthy air, hospitable and cheerful people, a prosperous and prosperous place, and many meek and pious people.

According to the historian A.Turobov, the name of the Sogdian state appears in the ancient Iranian written sources as Sogd, Sogd, Sokhd. In written sources, the Sughdians are often called Sogd, and the inhabitants of this country are called Sogdians, Sogdians. The name Sogd is mentioned in the Parthian inscription of the Sasanian king Shapur I (3rd century BC). The basis of the Sogdians is the nomadic and settled tribe of Saks. The Sogdians lived in the historical region in the basins of the Kashkadarya and Zarafshan rivers. First mentioned in the Avesta, books and cuneiforms of the era of Darius, and then in Chinese, Arabic and Persian medieval sources. The Sogdians became part of the Achaemenid state in the 6th-4th centuries BC. According to Herodotus, Sogdy, together with Parthia, Khorezm and Oria, constituted the II satrapy of the Akhomons.

Alexander the Great conquered Sogd in 329-327 BC. After his death, Sogd was subject to the Seleucid dynasty, the Kushan kingdom from the 1st century AD, the state of the Hephthalites at the end of the 4th century, until the 5th century AD, the Turkish Khanate in the 6th-7th centuries. centuries. At the end of the 7th century, beginning of the 8th century, Sogd was conquered by the Arabs. By the 11th century, the Sogdians living in Ettisuwa adopted the clothes and customs of the Turkic peoples. They spoke both Sughdian and Turkic. Later, the Sogdians were absorbed into the Turkic ethnic environment. [13; P.52]

Samarkand became the capital of the Timurid state in 1370. This process continued until the era of Shaybani Ubaydullah Khan (1533). Why did Timur choose Samarkand as the capital of his state? Some say that Samarkand was the largest of the first cities conquered by Temur, others say that this is because of the city's climate and the surrounding nature, which Timur liked, and still others say that Samarkand attracted Temur because it was known as a city

from ancient times. times, where it is assumed that the country of Turan was ruled by the famous Afrosiab.

In each of these assumptions, of course, there is some truth, but the objective reason for this, apparently, is that Samarkand, by its geographical position, is located in the center of Movarunnahr. There are rivers and springs around the city, and the city itself is surrounded by mountains on three sides, where three streams of air: from mountains, rivers, and also from fields - forests and meadows merge, and a calm climate stable. In the vicinity of Samarkand, there were large reserves of building materials, precious non-ferrous and rare metals. At that time, these riches could, to a certain extent, be put at the service of society.

Samarkand, according to Temur, was supposed to remain the most fertile city in the world; The fact that several large settlements were built around Samarkand, named after the main cities of Muslim countries, such as Baghdad, Damascus, Egypt (Cairo), Shiraz and the Sultanate, also confirms the above opinion. [14; P.99] Samarkand and the surrounding lands were surprisingly abundant and rich. Because of this wealth, the city is called Samarkand. Its real name is Semizkent, which means a rich village. Samarkand comes from this name.

Historians and poets describe Samarkand at the beginning of the 16th century as a populous, well-organized city with many markets, caravanserais, trade and craft workshops. Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, who has seen many cities of the East, in his memoirs describes Samarkand of that time as a «surprisingly comfortable city» with specialized markets and trading places. «This city has a feature» he says, «rarely found in other cities: a separate market is set aside for each craft and they do not mix with each other. This is a wonderful custom» [15, P.28].

RESULTS. The book «Samaria» by Abu Tahirkhoji Samarkandi (died in 1874) was written in the 50-60s of the 19th century and consists of an introduction, eleven chapters and a conclusion. The first chapter of the work is called «On the name of this city Samarkand», and here the interpretation of the toponym «Samarkand» is given in four versions:

There are several reasons why the city of Samarkand is called «Samarkand»:

firstly, in the book «Burkhoni Kote» it is mentioned that a man named Samar settled here and gathered people around him. That is why this place was originally called «Samarkent». When the Arab army captured this land, they changed it in their language to «Samarkand» (XVI century);

secondly, as mentioned in the book «Masolik ul-Mamolik», a khan named Samar Bakir came from Ferghana and Kashgar and destroyed the walls of the city because of enmity with the inhabitants of this region. Therefore, this city means «Samara mines». In Persian, it was called «Samarkand». After the Arab army took this city, it was called «Samarkand» (XI century);

thirdly, in the book «History of Tabari» it is mentioned that the Samara equestrian khan built this city, first of all, the Turkic region called «Kand» settled in it and killed. Therefore, this city was called «Samar + kand». After the Arab army took this city, it was called «Samarkand» (XI century);

fourthly, a source called «Samar» was dug out on the land of this city. Around this source people gathered and settled. For this reason, it became known as «Samarkand», after the name of the place. When the Arabs came, they said «Samarkand».

The city of Samarkand went down in history as the «beauty of the earth», «the pearl of the East», «ancient and famous city», «charming city», «reserved city», «seven climatic wonders», «trading port of Movarounnahr», «city-legend», «city-magic», «Bread City», «Eternal City» and other honorary names are proof of this.

CONCLUSION. It is concluded that the factors that made Samarkand Samarkand and turned it into the beauty of the Earth are its convenient geographical and strategic location, the fact that it was the center of trade, culture and science, as well as smart, hardworking and creative people who made the city blooming and beautiful. The toponym of Samarkand is also the fruit of this masterpiece of national thought.

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